

Reactive Methylene Compounds. Part VII. Condensations with Benzenediazonium Salts

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Several benzeneazo derivatives have been synthesised by coupling aromatic diazonium salts with 3,4-dichloro- and 2-chloro-5-methylbenzoyl-acetones, ω -anisoylacetophenone, and ω -benzoyl-3,4-dichloroacetophenone.

In previous communications of this series (Garg and Joshi, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 626; Garg, *ibid.*, 1961, 38, 113, 115), syntheses of the so-called benzeneazo derivatives of β -keto-esters and β -diketones were reported. The present communication describes the preparation of some more compounds. These are obtained by coupling of aromatic diazonium salts with reactive methylene compounds, such as, 3,4-dichloro-, 2-chloro-5-methylbenzoylacetones, ω -anisoylacetophenone, and ω -benzoyl-3,4-dichloroacetophenone.

All these compounds are highly coloured, crystalline solids. These are crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL **

3,4-Dichlorobenzoylacetone.—Sodium ethoxide (obtained from sodium, 2.3 g. and etha-ol, 12 c.c.) was treated with ethyl acetate (40 c.c.). 3,4-Dichloroacetophenone (0.1M) was added to the mixture, surrounded by ice, and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into ice water. The sodium salt of 3,4-dichlorobenzoylacetone separating was filtered and dried. The solid on acidification gave 3,4-dichlorobenzoylacetone. It was crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow solid, m.p. 84°, yield 52%. (Found : Cl, 30.62. $C_{10}H_6O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 30.73%).

2-Chloro-5-methylbenzoylacetone was similarly prepared by taking 2-chloro-5-methylacetophenone. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 61°, yield 54%. (Found : Cl, 16.84. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 16.86%).

ω -Benzoyl-3,4-dichloroacetophenone.—The synthesis was effected by the action of sodium methoxide on dibromide of benzylidene-3,4-dichloroacetophenone. It was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow crystals, m.p. 122°, yield 79%. (Found : Cl, 24.51. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24.23%).

ω -Anisoylacetophenone was prepared by a known method (Pond, Maxwell, and Normann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 21, 966).

Preparation of Benzeneazo Derivatives of β -Diketones

The benzeneazo compounds of substituted benzoylacetone and ω -benzoylacetophenones were obtained by the action of benzenediazonium chlorides on the corresponding β -diketones, as described earlier (*loc. cit.*). Characteristics of benzeneazo-substituted benzoylacetones and ω -benzoylacetophenones are recorded in Tables I and II respectively.

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** Melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE I
3,4-Dichlorobenzoylacetone.

No.	Substituted benzenezo derivative formed.	Yield	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Halogen. Found.	%Halogen. Calc.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Halogen. Found.	%Halogen. Calc.
1.	Benzenezo	86%	164°	Reddish yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	20.97	21.19	86%	122°	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	11.02	11.28
2.	4-Methoxy-	84	152°	Pale yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	19.03	19.45	84	127°	Golden yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	10.13	10.30
3.	4-Bromo-	92	140°	Light yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl ₂	36.17	36.47	92	142°	Canary yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl	28.97	29.35
4.	4-Chloro-	91	144°	Brownish "	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃	28.49	28.82	91	134°	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	20.11	20.34
5.	3-Chloro-	..	..	..	..	..	..	91	128°	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	20.21	20.34
6.	2-Chloro-	90	147°	Orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	28.52	28.82	90	136°	Light yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	19.93	20.34
7.	4-Nitro-	94	156°	Orange-red	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	18.83	18.68	95	144°	Light orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.59	9.87
8.	3-Nitro-	..	..	..	..	..	..	93	112°	Pale yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.61	9.87
9.	4-Methyl-	..	..	..	..	..	..	83	106°	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	10.53	10.80
10.	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	91	152°	Light yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	25.38	25.69	93	185°	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	17.81	18.02
11.	2-Nitro-4-chloro-	91	184°	Canary yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	25.41	25.69	92	138°	Golden yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	17.92	18.02

TABLE II

*No.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	ω-Anisoylacetophenone.		Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Halogen. Found.	%Halogen. Calc.	
				Formula.	Formula.							
1.	84%	142°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	N: 7.64	86%	124°	Brownish yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	17.79	17.88	
2.	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	
3.	88	175°	Golden yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	Br: 18.09	90	184°	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl ₂	31.58	31.72	
4.	87	166°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 8.88	89	164°	Pale yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	24.52	24.68	
5.	86	140°	Golden yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 8.92	9.04	..	..	..	..	..	
6.	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	
7.	90	159°	Pale yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	N: 10.28	10.42	88	126°	Dirty "	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	24.52	24.68
8.	90	146°	Light yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	N: 10.19	10.42	94	208°	Dirty "	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	15.92	16.06
9.	82	170°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	N: 7.41	7.52	93	166°	Dirty "	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	15.88	16.06
10.	89	162°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 7.91	8.11	..	..	..	..	..	..
11.	88	154°	Golden yellow	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	Cl: 7.94	8.11	93	176°	Light "	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	22.18	22.35

* The number of benzenezo derivatives corresponds to those listed in Table I.